

Leakage Mitigation of the Balongan–Plumpang Pipeline in the Cilincing Segment Using the CFO Method (Clamp, FRP, and Online Leak Sealing): Hydraulic Transient Analysis and Repair Clamp Strength Assessment

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Abstract

Pipeline systems transporting volatile liquids such as gasoline are vulnerable to transient pressure surges caused by sudden operational changes including valve closure, pump start-up, and pump shutdown. This study evaluates the transient hydraulic response, surge-induced mechanical effects, and the adequacy of a repair clamp design for a 16-inch gasoline pipeline segment from Booster Pump FT Cikampek to SDV-001 at FT Plumpang. The hydraulic transient simulation was performed using an in-house transient module, with the design flowrate set at 850 m³/h and fluid properties corresponding to Pertamina Turbo. Three surge scenarios were assessed: (1) SDV-001 fail-closed during two booster pump operation, (2) one booster pump start-up, and (3) one booster pump shutdown. Results indicate the maximum surge pressure reached 59 kg/cm² under the worst-case scenario, which remains below the Maximum Allowable Surge Pressure (MASP) of 87.60 kg/cm² (133% of design pressure 65.87 kg/cm²). Stress-related output included a surge force of approximately 703,184.97 N. Repair clamp strength evaluation at nodes 550 and 600 confirmed that bolt shear, bolt tension, flange strength, and slip checks satisfied unity check requirements ($UC < 1$), indicating the clamp design is adequate for the evaluated load cases. The study concludes that the pipeline system and clamp design remain within allowable limits for the considered transient events.

Keywords: Transient Surge; Water Hammer; Gasoline Pipeline; ASME B31.3; Hydraulic Analysis; Pipe Stress; Repair Clamp.

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1. Introduction

Pipeline integrity is a critical requirement in fuel distribution systems due to the high risk associated with transporting flammable and volatile liquids such as gasoline. Operational disturbances—such as rapid valve closure, pump trip, or sudden pump start-up—can generate transient pressure waves (surge) that propagate along the pipeline. These transient events may increase internal pressure and induce additional mechanical loads, potentially causing overstress, leakage, or failure at vulnerable locations including elbows, valves, and repair points.

This paper presents a case study of a gasoline fuel transfer pipeline evaluated by PT Dinamika Teknik Persada through hydraulic transient analysis, pipe stress assessment, and repair clamp capacity verification. The purpose is to ensure the pipeline remains within allowable limits during the most credible transient events and to verify that the clamp reinforcement design is adequate for the resulting forces and moments.

2. Methodology

2.1 Hydraulic Analysis

The methodology used in the hydraulic analysis is explained in the following subsection

2.1.1 Basis & Assumption

The following basis and assumptions are used in this study, changing the basis will subsequently change the study result.

2.1.1.1 Study Boundary

The hydraulic study is performed for 16” Gasoline Pipeline from Booster Pump FT Cikampek to SDV-001 in inlet FT Plumpang. The modelled system in Transient in house spreadsheet is as per green marked as follow:

Figure 01. Study Boundary for 16” Gasoline Pipeline

The following pressure is considered at study boundary

- Pump discharge pressure based on data recorded on Daily Check List Booster Pump refer to Table ...
- Inlet pressure at Fuel Terminal Plumpang : 7 kg/cm² g (refer to 13723399.JBB.RLA-PL-001)

2.1.1.2 Fluid characteristics

The following parameter is used for hydraulic calculation:

Table 01. Fluid Characteristics

Parameter	Value (Unit)
Fluid	Pertamax Turbo
Density	770 kg/m ³
Viscosity	0.45 cP
Bulk Modulus	1.05 x 10 ⁹ Pa
Vapor Pressure	-0.310 kg/cm ² a

2.1.1.3 Piping and Pipeline Properties

The following pipe and pipeline properties is used in the study:

General Design Condition

- Design Flowrate : 850 m³/h
- Maximum Allowable Surge Pressure (MASP) : 133% x Design Pressure (ASME B31.3)

16” Gasoline Pipeline from FT Cikampek to FT Plumpang

- Pipeline material : Carbon steel API-5L Gr. X46, Size: 16”
- Current thickness : 6.62 mm
- Young Modulus : 2.2 x 10¹¹ Pa
- Design pressure : 65.87 kg/cm² g (ANSI Class 600)
- Outside Diameter : 406 mm
- Inside Diameter : 393 mm

12” Pipe at FT Plumpang

- Pipeline Material : Carbon steel SCH 40, Size : 12”
- Current thickness : 9.53 mm
- Young Modulus : 2.2 x 10¹¹ Pa
- Design pressure : 65.87 kg/cm² g (ANSI Class 600)
- Outside Diameter : 381 mm

2.1.1.4 Pipeline Evaluation Data

The following pipeline elevation data is used for the study.

Table 02. Pipeline Elevation Data

Length (Kilometers)	Elevation (m)
0	0
94.75	-200

Notes:

1. Reference to the datum

2.1.1.5 Booster Pump

Due to lack of data, the shutoff pressure data is assumed with discharge pressure of 125% of the pressure in the maximum flowrate (i.e., 31.98 kg/cm² on total flowrate of 636 m³/h)

2.1.1.6 Shutdown Valve Data

Valve flow coefficient is required to be calculated in order to estimate the transient flowrate due to valve closing process. The valves CV are calculated with this equation:

$$CV = \frac{Q}{\sqrt{\Delta P}}$$

Where,

Cv = Flow coefficient, (m³/h)/(kg/cm²)^{0.5}

Q = Flowrate, m³/h

ΔP = pressure drop, kg/cm² g

Where above equation is used, the pressure drops across the valve is assumed to be 0.2 kg/cm²g. The valve characteristic for simulation is assumed as below:

Table 03. Valve Characteristic Simulation

Item	Size (Inch)	Q (m ³ /h)	ΔP (kg/cm ² g)	CV (m ³ /h)/(kg/cm ²) ^{0.5}	Opening/Closing (seconds)
SDV-001	12	850	0.2	129.25	12

Notes:

1. Faster opening/closing time will result in potentially higher surge pressure. The valve closing time of 1 sec/inch is taken, with total of 12 seconds.

2.1.2 Methodology

2.1.2.1 Simulation Schematics

Surge analysis is conducted using Inhouse Transient Module V.1.7. The simulation schematic is modelled based on the marked P&ID on Study Boundary Section 2.1.1.1.

Figure 02. Simulation Schematics

2.1.2.2 Model Build-Up

Time step of simulation is automatically calculated by the software according to parameters of each system (pipe length, wave speed, material, ...). It shall be in a range of 1-10 ms. Simulation durations are adapted according to scenarios. The wave velocity is defined for each circular pipes according to following formula:

$$c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\rho \left(\frac{Di}{eE} + \frac{1}{K} \right)}}$$

Where,

- c : Wave velocity (m/s)
- ρ : Density (kg/m³)
- Di : Pipe internal diameter (m)
- e : Pipe wall thickness (m)
- E : Young's Modulus of pipe (Pa)
- K : Bulk Modulus of Fluid (Pa)

2.1.2.3 Scenario

The following scenario will be performed:

1. Scenario 1 – SDV-001 at FT Plumpang Fail-Closed

In this scenario, the SDV-001 at downstream gasoline pipeline 16” in FT Plumpang is fail closed during two Booster Pump in FT Cikampek operating. During t=0s the system is performing in steady state condition then in t=4s the SDV-001 start closed.

2. Scenario 2 – One Booster Pump Start-Up

The Booster Pump in FT Plumpang is operated with 3 x 50% arrangement. This scenario considers the first pump already operating in steady state (at t=0s), and the second pump is started up (at t=4s).

3. Scenario 3 – One Booster Pump Shut Down

The Booster Pump in FT Plumpang is operated with 3 x 50% arrangement. This scenario considers the operating of two pumps in steady state (at t=0s), then one pump is failure and stopped (at t=4s).

2.2 Stress Analysis

This study employs a structured, multi-phase approach to evaluate surge-induced stress in pipeline systems. The methodology integrates theoretical analysis, simulation modeling, and reference to engineering standards. The methodology used in the pipe stress analysis is explained in the following subsection.

2.2.1 System Definition & Description

This study focuses on a gasoline fuel transfer pipeline system operating within a mid-scale distribution facility that starts from Booster pump at Cikampek to the Plumpang's receiving terminal. The system includes the following components and operational characteristics:

General Design Condition :

- Design Flowrate : 850 m³/h
- MASP : 133% Design Pressure
- Operating Pressure : 1.96133 bar
- Design Pressure : 65.87 kg/cm²
- Max. Surge pressure : 59.00 kg/cm²
- Max. Allowable Surge Pressure : 87.60 kg/cm²
- Velocity (as per design flowrate) : 1.9 m/s

Pipe Material Properties :

a. 16" Gasoline Pipeline from FT Cikampek to FT Plumpang

- Pipeline Material : Carbon steel API-5L Gr. X46, Size: 16", 6.62mm Thk (current thickness),
- Yield Strength : 320 N/mm²
- Ultimate Tensile Strength : 435 N/mm²
- Piping material density : 0.00783 Kg/cm³

b. 12" Pipe at FT Plumpang

- Pipeline Material : Carbon steel, Size: 12", SCH 40 (Thk 9.53mm)
- Young Modulus : 2.2 x 10¹¹ Pa
- Design Pressure : 65.87 kg/cm²
- OD : 381 mm

2.2.2 Surge Scenario Identification

Simulate operational events that may trigger surge, such as:

- Sudden valve closure [check valve]
- Pump trip or failure
- Emergency shutdown

Use transient flow modeling to replicate pressure wave propagation.

2.2.3 Analytical and Simulation Tools

Integrate pipeline design mechanical stress analysis using in-house spreadsheet with the code ASME B31.3 and B31.4

2.2.4 Stress Evaluation

Stress evaluation was performed by calculating the hoop stress, longitudinal stress, and combined stress of the pipeline under surge conditions. The calculated stress results were then compared with the allowable stress limits based on the pipeline material properties and the applicable design codes to confirm that the system remains within acceptable safety margins.

2.2.5 Risk Assessment & Mitigation

1. Identify critical stress points and failure risks.
2. Recommend mitigation strategies such as:
 - Surge relief valves
 - Controlled valve actuation
 - Pipeline reinforcement or re-routing

2.3 Clamp Analysis

The methodology integrates theoretical analysis, spreadsheet analysis, and reference to engineering standards. The methodology used in the pipe clamp analysis is explained in the following subsection.

2.3.1 Study Boundary

The pipe clamp calculation analysis is located at node 550 and 600, as marked in the following figure.

Figure 03. Pipe Clamp Location for Analysis at Node 550 and 600

2.3.2 Material Specification

The material specifications used for the pipe clamp calculation analysis are as follows:

- Bolt Material : ASTM A193-B7
- Bolt Tensile Strength : 125 Ksi
- Number of Bolt : 6 pcs
- Clamp Plate Material : ASTM A516 Grade 70
- Clamp Plate Modulus Elasticity : 29000 Ksi

2.3.3 Clamp Configuration

The configuration and dimensions of the pipe clamp based on the obtained data can be seen in the following Table and Figure:

Table 04. Clamp Configuration Data

No	Parameter	Specification
1	Distance between bolts	87.5 mm
2	Distance from bolt to edge	87.5 mm
3	Bolt diameter	2- ³ / ₈ inch
4	Stud diameter	1- ¹ / ₂ inch
5	X max	252.5 mm
6	Tubular diameter (OD)	455.1 mm
7	Inner diameter of clamp late (ID)	16.5 inch (419.1 mm)
8	Thickness of clamp (t clamp)	97 mm
9	Flange width	121 mm
10	Effective clamp length (L)	350 mm
11	Flange Thickness	94 mm

Figure 04. The Sketch of Clamp Configuration

2.3.4 Forces & Moments

The forces and moments used for the pipe clamp calculation analysis at node 550 and 600 results from stress analysis.

2.3.5 Calculation of Tension and Shear Force in Bolt

The calculation of the resultant tensile and shear forces on the clamp bolts is carried out based on the bolt configuration and the force output acting on the pipe clamp. The resulting forces are then compared with the shear and tensile capacities of the bolts according to their material specifications.

2.3.6 Clamp Strength Check

The strength calculation of the clamp is performed on the body of the pipe clamp and its stiffeners. The analysis considers the hoop stress, bolt torque, and bolt slip resulting from the forces acting on the clamp body.

3. Result & Discussion

3.1 Hydraulic Analysis

1. Transient Scenario 1 – SDV-001 at FT Plumpang Fail-Closed

In this scenario, the SDV-001 at downstream gasoline pipeline 16” in FT Plumpang is fail closed during two Booster Pump in FT Cikampek operating. During $t=0s$ the system is performing in steady state condition then in $t=4s$ the SDV-001 start closed. Based on the case, the maximum pressure on the system is as per the following figure:

Figure 05. Maximum Pressure on Pipeline (in kg/cm² a) – scenario 1

Figure 06. Pressure Evolution – Scenario 1

Based on the simulation, the maximum pressure in the system if SDV-001 fail closed during Booster Pump #1 and Booster Pump #2 is operating is 59 kg/cm² a. The maximum allowable surge pressure (MASP) of the pipeline is 87.60 kg/cm² a (133% of design pressure of 65.87 kg/cm² a) and the maximum surge pressure during scenario 1 is 59 kg/cm² a. Hence, it is concluded that maximum surge pressure is lower than MASP and design pressure. It is considered acceptable.

2. Transient Scenario 2 – One Booster Pump Start-Up

The Booster Pump in FT Plumpang is operated with 3 x 50% arrangement. This scenario considers the first pump already operating in steady state (at $t=0s$), and the second pump is started up (at $t=4s$). Based on the case, the maximum pressure on the system is as per the following figure:

Figure 07. Maximum Pressure on Pipeline (in $kg/cm^2 a$) – scenario 2

Figure 08. Pressure Evolution – scenario 2

Based on the simulation, the maximum pressure in the system Booster Pump #2 start-up during Booster Pump #1 operating is $29.49 kg/cm^2 a$. The maximum allowable surge

pressure (MASP) of the pipeline is $87.60 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \text{ a}$ (133% of design pressure of $65.87 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \text{ a}$) and the maximum surge pressure during scenario 2 is $29.49 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \text{ a}$. Hence, it is concluded that maximum surge pressure is lower than MASP and design pressure. It is considered acceptable.

3. Transient Scenario 3 – One Booster Pump Shutdown

The Booster Pump in FT Plumpang is operated with 3 x 50% arrangement. This scenario considers the operating of two pumps in steady state (at $t=0\text{s}$), then one pump is failure and stopped (at $t=4\text{s}$). Based on the case, the maximum pressure on the system is as per the following figure:

Figure 09. Maximum pressure on Pipeline (in $\text{kg/cm}^2 \text{ a}$) – scenario 3

Figure 10. Pressure Evolution – scenario 3

Based on the simulation, the maximum pressure in the system during Booster Pump #2 failure and Booster Pump #1 operating is 29.50 kg/cm² a. The maximum allowable surge pressure (MASP) of the pipeline is kg/cm² a (133% of design pressure of kg/cm² a) and the maximum surge pressure during scenario 3 is 29.50 kg/cm² a. Hence, it is concluded that maximum surge pressure is lower than MASP and design pressure. It is considered acceptable.

3.2 Stress Analysis

Due to the large number of nodes generated in the pipe stress model, only critical locations corresponding to the leakage points (Node 550 and Node 600) are reported in this paper. The extracted forces and moments at these nodes were subsequently used as the governing load inputs for the clamp strength assessment.

- Surge Force 703184.97 N

Table 05. Pipe Stress Analysis Force and Moment Results

Node	Member Force (Kips)			Moment (Kips-Inch)		
	Fy	Fx	Fz	My	Mx	Mz
550	0.026	129.206	0.028	12.037	1.531	8.683
600	0.026	129.206	0.028	15.356	1.407	16.701

3.3 Clamp Analysis

The calculations have been carried out using in-house spreadsheet, that has generated some outputs with summary as below:

Node 550:

- Unity Check (Shear) = 0,4570 UC < 1 OK
- Unity Check (Tension) = 0,0034 UC < 1 OK
- Flange Strength Check = 0,1166 UC < 1 OK
- Allowable hoop stress calculation = 19,3934 SF > 2 OK, Clamp is adequate
- Check for Slip or Sliding = 0,5871 UC < 1 OK
- Check for Torsional / Radial Slip = 0,0002 UC < 1 OK

Node 600:

- Unity Check (Shear) = 0,4574 UC < 1 OK
- Unity Check (Tension) = 0,0047 UC < 1 OK
- Flange Strength Check = 0,1166 UC < 1 OK
- Allowable hoop stress calculation = 19,3934 SF > 2 OK, Clamp is adequate
- Check for Slip or Sliding = 0,5871 UC < 1 OK
- Check for Torsional / Radial Slip = 0,0002 UC < 1 OK

All calculations in the pipe clamp analysis have met the requirements where the unity check results in a value less than 1

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

Based on the study it is concluded that

- The maximum surge pressure on the pipeline is 59 kg/cm^2 and it is lower than maximum allowable surge pressure (MASP) of 87.60 kg/cm^2 and design pressure of 65.87 kg/cm^2 . This is considered acceptable.
- All calculations in the pipe clamp analysis have met the requirements where the unity check results in a value less than 1
- Overall, the pipeline system and clamp design are considered acceptable for the analyzed transient scenarios.

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